

CONSUMERS' PERCEPTION ON MARKETING STRATEGIES ADOPTED BY SELECT RETAILERS IN ONLINE MARKET

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Abstract

The Internet has transformed the conventional methods of doing business, ultimately causing more difficulties in the online marketing system. Nowadays, due to free access to the plethora of information available, online buyers need not be depended dependent on a salesperson. Because of more comprehensive coverage, online shopping has simplified the way of shopping and has gained hype not only from customers but from retailers as well. Customers select online shopping for different reasons, with convenience and belief being the chief factors next to prices and superiority of products. The study established the level of influence of different marketing strategies adopted by e-retailers. Data has been collected from 450 respondents through a primary source, for which the interview schedule was used. SPSS 20 has been used to analyze and interpret data. T-test, ANOVAs and chi-square analysis have been used. Study results show that marketing strategies adopted by different leading online retailers have significant differences towards influencing the customers to shop through the online market.

Keywords: Marketing Strategies, Influencing, Online-retailers and Online Marketing.

INTRODUCTION

In the last two decades there has been a rapid growth of e-commerce in India. The penetration of mobile and internet connections has transformed the way of communication. While compared with some developed countries like the United States, United Kingdom, and Canada, online shopping is still at a nascent stage in India, but it is growing very fast. This growth has been propelled by the quick adoption of technology, especially because of more access to the internet and broadband, use of tablets and smart phones, betterment of standards of living and the growing middle class. The Internet has completely changed the way transactions happen and online shopping is one of the most important ones. Since the year 2000, online shopping has been present in India. It became popular with the introduction of the deep discount model of different websites. In a way, it was instrumental in relaunching online shopping. The digital transformation happening in India is increasing the e-commerce revenue to US\$ 120 billion in 2020, up from 39 billion in 2017. The growth rate is being 51%, the highest in the world. Average annual e-commerce sales per digital buyer in India were 424 U.S. dollars in 2020.

The response of the consumer indicates their post-purchase behavior, it provides suggestions to others about the willingness of online retailers' service and also can understand whether the customers' expectations have been fulfilled or not. Customers' decisions and their views about the site are known as trust. Trust is a significant perception of online shopping. In online

shopping, trust refers to customers' beliefs in the platform's competence and the excellent aspects of the online services, i.e., website design, privacy, security, efficiency, communications with customers, particularly their confidentiality of buyers' sensitive information, such as credit card details that may lead to fraud, should data be disclosed. Psychological factors likewise motivate customers' preference, perceptions, trust, and attitudes towards spending habits. Recognizing factors affecting consumers' preferences and attitudes will help to take necessary steps to increase their satisfaction with the online retailers' services. Studying post-purchase attitudes is the source of signposting whether they will make repeat practice and recommend the particular online retailers' services to others or not.

It will help the online retailers to estimate the expected long-term profits. Consumers' satisfaction cannot be widespread; it is desired by a number of factors. If consumers are dissatisfied with services, they start to denigrate the services and spread the services' undesirable characteristics to their friends, peers and associates; they discontinue usage of those particular retailers and change to a new online retailer or a new one. Due to the availability of suitable a alternative, some unhappy consumers continue to repeat purchasers, but buy them owing to the force of habit or low prices. Some committed consumers are attached to the brand emotionally, it shows their brand loyalty, i.e., believe and trust the online retailers. In this section of the study an attempt was made to find out the factors influencing the customers towards the selection of online retailers' services.

GAPS IN LITERATURE

Researchers have visited several studies relating to online shopping and customers' perception and satisfaction of online services. Most of the studies have analysed the difference between traditional and online marketing sideways with the variation of several services. In the marketing field, online marketing is still emerging. Hence, the literature is lacking particularly in factors influencing customers to move towards online shopping and the selection of online retailers' services. Hence, this study fills the gap by conducting research on factors influencing customers to go for online shopping.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

The study is of significance for present / future online marketers, and also for financial designers and market agents for making marketing strategies and plans. The present study would help the e-retailer providers to add value and achieve a competitive edge against their competitors and remain successful in the long run, and the study would recognize the most important marketing strategy that highly influencing their consumers' behavior would disturb their future strategies. This helps the general public and online traders to take necessary steps to improve customer satisfaction with development strategies.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Commerce through the electronic version came into worldwide prospect. It is sure to wait and rule the world for a long time in future eras, making inventions and revolutions of the last

century across the world. The comfort, the ease, the quickness, lower cost, global access is the few of the vital things to go for online-shopping. Online-retailing is a form of virtual retailing service that delivers different goods ordered on the internet to a place defined by the customers. The success of online retail lies in the formulation of an effective strategy and operations. To reach more consumers and earn more revenue, some of the online marketers have adopted many types of marketing strategies, namely,. Search engine optimization, pay per click, content marketing, Social media, Email marketing, Web design, Conversion rate optimization (CRO), Reputation management, Influencer marketing etc. social In India online retailing is still at its growth stage. There is a need for development of new marketing strategies to get hits to e-stores. In the present situation of the changing retail landscape, it is very important for online retailers to build strong relationships with consumers to achieve customer loyalty to the web store. In order to create a loyal customer, online retailers need to strengthen their strategies. With several companies offering such close and yet different products, several questions that emerge are given about products and services and consumer preferences. A need is identified to study the particular factors influencing customers to move towards online shopping and the selection of online retailers' services. In this background, the study has elevated the following research questions: What are the marketing strategies followed by the online retailers? What are the marketing strategies of online marketers that attract consumers to purchase a product from the online market?

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Keeping in view, questions raised above, the objectives of the present study include

To analyse, the marketing strategies adopted by select online retailers are generic or different.

To examine the level of factors influencing the selection of online retailers' marketing strategies

HYPOTHESES

The following hypothesis was formulated and tested in the present study.

Ho1: There is no significant difference in marketing strategies adopted by select retailers in the online market.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in level of influence towards the selection of online retailers for online shopping.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This research work is to study the perception of online customers in Cuddalore district. So far, this type of attempt has not been made in this field and it is necessary to do research in this area. Through many retailers in the online market, the study was conducted only with the consumer from the selected five online retailers, namely Amazon.com, Flipkart, Snapdeal, Myntra and Shopclues associated with online markets in Cuddalore district. This district has

numerous small and medium scale industries and provides more employment opportunities. Hence, this district is considered for the present study and made an attempt to examine the perception of consumers on different strategies offered by online retailers. The study compared select online retailers' marketing strategies from the viewpoint of consumers.

Research Design

Based on the objectives of the study, the researcher has chosen a pathway of descriptive research design. The current study is based on primary data. The primary data was collected through a structured interview schedule. The researcher proposed to purposely select Cuddalore District in Tamilnadu, India for the research. Cuddalore District consists of three revenue divisions, i.e., Cuddalore revenue division, Chidambaram revenue division, Virudhachalam revenue division. Out of three divisions, Cuddalore's revenue division (33.33%) has been selected. Cuddalore's revenue division consists of three taluks, Cuddalore, Panruti, and Kurinjipadi of which Cuddalore taluks (33.33%) has been selected. The number of rural (villages) in this taluk is 82, of which 8 are town limits and the other 74 are rural (village) limit. Out of 8 town limits 3 (33.33%) and out of 74 village limits, 24 (33.33%) were randomly selected for the study. 75 respondents from each selected town and 10 respondents from each selected village were selected. Hence, the total sample size for the study is 465 respondents. Due to incomplete response, 15 interview schedules were excluded and, finally, 450 samples were considered for the present study.

Reliability Analysis

The reliability of the information collected from the respondents was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha. The Cronbach's alpha allows measuring the reliability of the different categories through measuring the average correlation among the observed variables. In this study, the Cronbach's alpha yielded acceptable ranges of reliability coefficients and it tells the consistency of the interview schedule. The KMO measure of sampling adequacy was computed to determine the suitability of using factor analysis. The value of 0.781 obtained was indicative of a more than moderate category. Hence, factor analysis can be carried out on the responses collected from the respondents.

Factor loading represents a correlation between an original variable and its factors. Further, the five factors that defined these characteristics have been assigned suitable names according to the variables loaded on each factors. These five factors are financial factors, product and delivery, convenience design and convenience, safety and security of information and after-sale service.

The first factor, 'Financial factors' financial consists of eight variables explaining 24.660 % of the total variance. The second important factor, 'Product and Delivery', covered five statements with the highest explained variance of 20.856 %. Factor three is 'Web site design and convenient' with the highest explained variance of 18.159 %. This factor has covered ten statements. The fourth factor 'Safety and Security of information' accounted for 5.568 % of the variance. The fifth factor "After sales service" accounted for 2.746 % of the variance.

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS' LEVEL OF INFLUENCE AND SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE

In this part of the study, the researcher made an attempt to ascertain whether there was significant difference in the influence of factors according to selected online retailers; the ANOVA test and an independent sample t-test were applied.

Financial Factors' Level of Influence

The following table presents the opinion of the respondents about the finance related factors influencing consumers' decision towards the selection of online retailers while shopping online.

Table 1: Respondents Opinion on Level of Influenced By Finance Related Factors

Statements	Mean	Rank
Low price	3.86	1
Navigation methods	3.73	2
No harassment	3.58	4
Move from one page to another	3.68	3

Source: Computed from collected primary data : Figures given in parenthesis are percentage to row total

It has been observed from Table 1 that the average score of 'low price' reaches a maximum of 3.86 and is ranked in the first position of the product characters. The average score for the navigation methods is 3.73 and ranked two. The respondents agreed that moving from one page to another is considered as another important important; its average score is 3.71 and it ranked third. Respondents believe that there is no harassment. The average score for the factor less financial risk is 3.58 and ranked four.

PRODUCT AND DELIVERY FACTORS' LEVEL OF INFLUENCE

The opinion of the respondents about the price related factors' level of influencing the consumers' purchase decision while selecting online retailers. The following table 2 presents the results.

Table 2: Respondents Opinion on Level of Influence by Product and Delivery Related Factors

Statements	Mean	Rank
Availability wide range of product verities and choice	3.91	3
Availability of rare products	4.20	1
Security and Reliability of information	3.62	5
Easy and convenience for shopping	3.80	4
Speed purchase	4.08	2

Source: Computed from collected primary data Figures given in parenthesis are percentage to row total

It has been observed from Table 2 that the majority of the respondents strongly believe that the availability of rare products is highly influenced (mean 4.20 rank 1). The average score for the speed purchase is 4.08 and ranked two. The average score for availability of a wide range of product versions and choices is 3.91 and ranked third. The average score for Easy and convenience for shopping is 3.80 and ranked four. Similarly, security and reliability of information ranked in place. Its average score is 3.62.

Web Site Design and Convenient Factors' Level of Influence

The opinion of the respondents about the Web site design and convenient factors influencing the consumers' online retailer selection decision is presented in the following Table 3.

Table 3: Respondents Opinion on Level of Influenced By Web Site Design and Convenient Related Factors

Statements	Mean	Rank
Easy comparison of product and service	3.56	8
High discount and schemes	4.13	1
Easy gathering information	3.67	4
Easy payment mechanism	3.86	2
Quick delivery	3.51	9
Access to global markets	3.62	7
Less stress	3.64	6
Advertisement and other sale promotion	3.76	3
Less Expensive	3.65	5
Service Quality	3.51	9

Source: Computed from collected primary data Figures given in parenthesis are percentage to row total

It has been observed from Table 3 that the average score for high discount and scheme factor is 4.13 and is ranked in the first position on price-related factors. The payment mechanism is considered as another important factor for choosing E-service providers. The average score for the factor is 3.86 and ranked two. The advertisement and other sales promotion's average score is 3.76 and ranked third. The average score for gathering easily is 3.67 and ranked four. The average scores for less expenses and less stress are 3.65 and 3.64, respectively, and ranked in fifth and sixth places. Access to global markets and easy comparison of product and service are considered as influencing factors listed in the seventh and eighth ranks. Quick delivery and service quality are equally considered as influencing factors listed in the ninth rank.

Safety and Security of Information Factors' Level of Influence

The respondents' opinion on the safety and security of information factors influencing online retailers' selection decisions. The following table 4 presents the results.

Table 4: Respondents Opinion on Level of Influenced By Safety and Security of Information And Selected Online Retailers

Statements	Mean	Rank
Having understandable content	3.95	3
Providing better customized content	4.04	2
Similarity to other website's like Twitter, Gmail etc	4.17	1
Providing helpful suggestions to prevent from mistakes	3.93	4

Source: Computed from collected primary data Figures given in parenthesis are percentage to row total

It has been observed from Table 4 that similarities to other websites like Twitter, Gmail etc, providing better customized content, having understandable content, and providing helpful suggestions to prevent mistakes are highly influencing consumers. These factors hold the first four ranks in order. The average scores for these four factors are 4.17, 4.04, 3.95 and 3.93 respectively.

After Sales Service Factors' Level of Influence

The following table 5 presents the opinion of the respondents about the after-sales service factors influencing consumers in online retailers' selection decisions.

Table 5: Respondents Opinion on Level of Influenced By After Sales Service Selected Online Retailers

Statements	Mean	Rank
Presenting error messages good understandable manner	3.95	3
Better navigation for going to previous page, exit	3.89	4
Having better call to action (favourites, add to wish list) button	4.04	2
Providing better help/assistance and documentation after adding a product to cart	3.68	5
Providing freedom of editing personal information	4.17	1

Source: Computed from collected primary data Figures given in parenthesis are percentage to row total

It has been observed from Table 5 that the average score for providing freedom of editing personal information makes people is 4.17, ranked in the first position in after-sales service factor. Having a better call to action (favourites, add to wish list) button is considered as the second factor for choosing of online retailers. The average score is 4.04. Presenting error messages in a good understandable, the average score is 3.95 and I ranked third. The better navigation for going to the previous page, exit make them selection online retailer. The average score is 3.95 and ranked four. Providing better help/assistance and documentation after adding a product to the cart is ranked fifth. Its average score is 3.89.

Respondents' Gender and Influencing Factors

To test the significant difference in influence, the following statistical hypothesis is formulated and tested. Ho: There is no significant difference in level of influences towards e-influence services in online shopping between respondents among different genders” In order to analyse

the difference in the influence level, a simple t-test was applied and the result is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Level of Factors Influence – Comparison by Gender

Influence Factors	Gender		t-Value
	Male	Female	
Financial Factors	3.64 (0.71)	3.55 (0.67)	1.31
Product and Delivery	3.64 (0.71)	3.59 (0.80)	0.64
Web site Design and Convenient	3.89 (0.72)	3.74 (0.84)	2.41*
Safety and Security of Information	3.63 (0.94)	3.49 (0.89)	1.48
After sales Service	3.59 (0.96)	3.49 (0.91)	1.38
Overall influence	3.70 (0.70)	3.64 (0.69)	1.87

Source: Computed from collected primary data, Figures given in parenthesis are standard deviations *Significant at 5% level; **Significant at 1% level

As per the result, the level of influence on all five factors is higher for male respondents compared to that of female counterparts. However, the difference in the mean influence scores between the two gender groups is significant only in respect of Web site Design and Convenient (t value = 2.41, $p < 0.00$). That is, the level of influence of male respondents on website design and convenience is significantly higher compared to that of female respondents. At the same time, the overall influence is the same between the two groups. Hence, it is concluded that there is no difference in factors' level of influence on selection the e-retailers services in online shopping between male and female respondents in the study region. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Respondents' Age and Influencing Factors

To test the significant difference in influence, the following statistical hypothesis is formulated and tested. Ho: There is no significant difference in influence of influences on e-retailer services in online shopping between respondents among different age groups” In order to analyse the difference in the influence level, the F-test was applied and the result is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Level of Factors Influence – Comparison by Age Levels

Influence Factors	Age Levels (in Years)					F-Value
	Below 20	20-30	30-40	40-50	Above 50	
Financial Factors	3.58 (0.72)	3.55 (0.70)	3.31 (0.88)	3.79 (0.69)	3.64 (0.70)	0.46
Product and Delivery	3.61 (0.81)	3.57 (0.71)	3.83 (0.97)	3.61 (0.71)	3.75 (0.79)	0.32
Web site Design and Convenient	3.67 (0.81)	3.72 (0.76)	3.41 (0.98)	3.66 (0.89)	3.59 (0.94)	0.40
Safety and Security of Information	3.57 (0.90)	3.58 (0.84)	3.70 (0.97)	3.81 (0.77)	3.80 (0.76)	1.63*
After sales Service	3.85 (0.68)	3.66 (0.72)	3.42 (0.94)	3.66 (0.81)	3.52 (0.92)	0.59
Overall influence	3.70 (0.72)	3.61 (0.97)	3.72 (0.88)	3.70 (0.69)	3.69 (0.94)	0.60

Source: Computed from collected primary data, Figures given in parenthesis are standard deviations *Significant at 5% level; **Significant at 1% level

Table 7 presents the results of the F-test comparing the level of influence of factors. As per the result, the Safety and Security of Information factor has significant differences in level of influence among different age groups.

Other factors like Financial, Product and Delivery, Website Design and Convenient and After-sales Service significantly differ. Overall influence is the same among five different age groups.

Hence, it is concluded that there is no difference in factors' level of influence on the selection of e-retailer services for the online shopping among the different five age groups of respondents in the study region. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Respondents' Educational Qualification and Influencing Factors

To test the significant difference in influence, the following statistical hypothesis is formulated and tested. Ho: There is no significant difference in influence on e-retailer services on online shopping between respondents among different educational qualifications." In order to analyse the difference in the influence level, the F-test was applied and the result is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Level of Factors Influence – Comparison by Educational Qualification

Influence Factors	Educational Qualification						F-Value
	Upto School level	Under graduate	Post graduate	Professional Degree	Diploma and Certificate Level	Technical Degree	
Financial Factors	3.77 (0.70)	3.59 (0.82)	3.64 (0.69)	3.54 (0.76)	3.49 (0.72)	3.53 (0.67)	1.82
Product and Delivery	3.77 (0.76)	3.81 (0.60)	3.60 (0.71)	3.51 (0.86)	3.61 (0.58)	3.58 (0.70)	3.97**
Web site Design and Convenient	3.52 (0.75)	3.91 (0.66)	3.77 (0.70)	3.61 (0.79)	3.72 (0.63)	3.71 (0.58)	2.71**
Safety and Security of Information	3.51 (0.84)	3.42 (0.72)	3.65 (0.64)	3.28 (0.68)	3.22 (0.69)	3.63 (0.61)	4.67*
After sales Service	3.60 (0.75)	3.69 (0.80)	3.82 (0.61)	3.61 (0.66)	3.67 (0.77)	3.79 (0.60)	1.92
Overall influence	3.44 (0.81)	3.59 (0.86)	3.54 (0.84)	3.62 (0.87)	3.55 (0.84)	3.51 (0.82)	3.73*

Source: Computed from collected primary data, Figures given in parenthesis are standard deviations *Significant at 5% level; **Significant at 1% level

From the perusal of Table 8, it is understood that out of five categories of factors influencing the respondents having different educational qualifications, three factors like product and delivery, convenience, design and convenience and safety and security of information, are similarly influenced by the selection of e-retailers' services in online shopping. Hence, it is concluded that factors' level of influence on selection the e-retailers services in online shopping among different educated groups of respondents is significantly differ in the study region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents' Occupation and Influencing Factors

To test the significant difference in influence, the following statistical hypothesis is formulated and tested. Ho: There is no significant difference in level of influences towards e-influence services in online shopping between respondents among influence to occupations” In order to analyse the difference in the influence level, a one-way ANOVA test was applied and the result is presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Level of Factors Influence – Comparison by Occupational Status

Influence Factors	Occupational Status						F-Value
	Self-employed Unemploy	Employed Government employee	Business and profession	Retired Business	Students and Home maintena	Farmers and others Students	
Financial Factors	3.27 (0.69)	3.65 (0.74)	3.68 (0.75)	3.64 (0.69)	3.86 (0.71)	3.39 (0.70)	4.98**
Product and Delivery	3.48 (1.12)	3.71 (0.78)	3.77 (0.76)	3.69 (0.70)	3.70 (0.71)	3.58 (1.01)	4.42**
Web site Design and Convenient	3.75 (0.91)	3.71 (0.76)	3.67 (0.74)	3.74 (0.76)	3.81 (0.79)	3.77 (0.91)	2.89
Safety and Security of Information	3.41 (0.94)	3.66 (0.81)	3.59 (0.91)	3.58 (0.83)	3.62 (0.93)	3.51 (0.87)	3.58*
After sales Service	3.62 (0.78)	3.69 (0.68)	3.74 (0.69)	3.85 (0.78)	3.76 (0.69)	3.52 (0.79)	4.58**
Overall influence	3.79 (1.18)	3.78 (0.82)	3.77 (0.83)	3.69 (0.77)	3.77 (0.76)	3.59 (0.78)	4.64**

Source: Computed from collected primary data, Figures given in parenthesis are standard deviations *Significant at 5% level; **Significant at 1% level

From the perusal of Table 9, it is understood that out of five categories of factors that influence the respondents having different occupations, four factors like financial factors , product and delivery, safety and security of information and by sales service are not similarly influenced by the selection of e-retailers’ services in online shopping.

Hence, it is concluded that factors’ level of influence on selection the e-retailers services in online shopping among six different occupational respondents were significantly different in the study region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Family Annual Income of the Respondent

To test the significant difference in influence, the following statistical hypothesis is formulated and tested.

Ho: There is no significant difference in the influence of influences towards e-retailer services on online shopping between respondents with different annual income” In order to invest the difference in the influence level, the analyzed-way ANOVA test was applied and the result is presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Level of Factors Influence – Comparison by Family Annual Income

Influence Factors	Family Annual Income			F-Value
	Less than Rs.5,00,000	Rs.5,00,000 to 10,00,000	More than Rs. 10,00,000	
Financial Factors	3.52 (0.71)	3.60 (0.70)	3.69 (0.71)	3.48**
Product and Delivery	3.60 (0.62)	3.69 (0.68)	3.47 (0.66)	3.74**
Web site Design and Convenient	3.58 (0.74)	3.69 (0.70)	3.71 (0.70)	3.34**
Safety and Security of Information	3.59 (0.81)	3.76 (0.77)	3.69 (0.81)	3.88**
After sales Service	3.68 (0.77)	3.44 (0.64)	3.64 (0.58)	4.30**
Overall influence	3.80 (0.98)	3.74 (0.80)	3.82 (0.60)	4.45**

Source: Computed from collected primary data, Figures given in parenthesis are standard deviations *Significant at 5% level; **Significant at 1% level

From the perusal of the Table 10, it is understood that all the five categories of factors influencing the respondents having different family income groups are not similarly influenced by the selection of e-retailers' services in online shopping. Hence, it is concluded that factors' level of influence on the selection of e-retailers service three different types of annual income respondents significantly different in the study region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Respondents Residential Area

To test the significant difference in influence, the following statistical hypothesis is formulated and tested. Ho: There is no significant difference in influence on e-retailer services on online shopping among respondents in different residential areas." In order to analyse the difference in the influence level, a simple t- test was applied and the result is presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Level of Factors Influence – Comparison by Residential Area

Influence Factors	Residential Area		t-Value
	Urban	Non-urban	
Financial Factors	3.59 (0.49)	3.67 (0.57)	2.88**
Product and Delivery	3.48 (0.57)	3.57 (0.60)	3.62**
Web site Design and Convenient	3.18 (0.71)	3.00 (0.58)	2.27**
Safety and Security of Information	3.54 (0.64)	3.77 (0.74)	3.44*
After sales Service	3.70 (0.77)	3.79 (0.74)	3.11**
Overall influence	3.76 (0.69)	3.75 (0.65)	3.61*

Source: Computed from collected primary data, Figures given in parenthesis are standard deviations *Significant at 5% level; **Significant at 1% level

From the perusal of Table 11, it is understood that all the five categories of factors influencing the respondents having different residential area groups are not similarly influenced by the selection of e-retailers' services in online shopping. Hence, it is concluded that factors' level of influence on selection the e-retailers services in online shopping among respondents' residential area significantly different in the study region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

CONCLUSION

The marketing strategy involves deciding on the details of the intended decisions of the marketing strategy on goal selection, choice of market and customer target. Strong marketing strategies are clearly important to the effectiveness of an organisation and so the effectiveness of the marketing strategy creating processes is a crucial thought for each academic and practitioners. To achieve vision, marketing strategies have made progress in acquiring a large market share in the facility service industry. As the study finds, the right marketing strategies for retailer would be based on a number of factors such as size of market, economic, political, social etc, and most importantly, online retailers' marketing strategies have significantly differed in influencing customers to shop through the online market.

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